

WAYS TO IMPROVE MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN TEXTILE ENTERPRISES

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***Abstract.** In this article, maximum adaptation of the production and trade activities of the textile industry to the requirements of specific consumers, the main goal of consumer market segmentation, determining the specific characteristics of consumers, The strategy of innovative development of the market of industrial products, the organization of gross marketing activities of marketing research, its management, planning and control are discussed.*

***Keywords:** enterprise, product, market, demand, supply, innovation, price, competition.*

Introduction. The strategy for innovative development of the light industry market allows for the economic assessment of the export potential of the industry based on the formation of supply and demand for the garment market, the study of the domestic and foreign markets, and the formation of an information and advertising system. In our opinion, forecasting supply and demand for the industry's products, increasing the volume of processing natural fibers, manufacturing new types of fabrics based on innovations, and adapting new production technologies to local raw materials should be the main directions of the strategy for the development of the garment market. In implementing this strategy, the training of highly qualified personnel, their continuous professional development and retraining are of particular importance. After all, no matter how good the ideas are, no matter how good the best equipment and technologies are, high results cannot be achieved without qualified personnel.

Marketing research is of great importance in the innovative development of light industry in our republic. Such activities allow for the analysis of the international market, research of product sales markets, study of marketing operations, collection and processing of information, research of the marketing mix, study of competitors, benchmarking, forecasting of demands and sales.

In the analytical function of marketing research, the factors of the external environment, the market, its elements and situation, consumers, the market, the product and the structure of the product, as well as the internal environment of the firm are analyzed. Factors controlled by the company's management are taken into account - technological process, financial situation, organizational structure, market selection, etc. External environmental factors include uncontrollable factors such as consumers, competition, government, economy, technology, independent media.

The reduction of centralized planning bodies in the textile industry in a market economy requires independent movement in the formation and maintenance of branched and complex relationships. Accordingly, it is necessary to use the methods of market segmentation to produce effective plans for the development of the textile industry.

Market segmentation is the process of dividing consumers and sellers of textile products into segments based on their needs and reactions in the market. The marketing concept in the trade sector is based on the fact that sellers use the product differently and buy it based on different

motivations. The textile industry needs to adapt its production and sales activities to the needs of specific consumers as much as possible. The main goal of consumer market segmentation is to group all consumers into products of the same type as much as possible.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In the economic literature, there are many different views on the essence and concept of efficiency, as well as its various criteria and indicators are classified. Many authors emphasize that efficiency is a relative indicator and recommend that it be determined by the ratio of costs to the obtained (achieved) result.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing in the economy, while the researches conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years stemmed from national characteristics. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov, Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkho'jaev, B. Khodiev, K. Mirzayev, SH. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musaeva and others can be included.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. A consumer market segment must meet a number of requirements:

1. Each segment should be clearly described.
2. It is necessary to identify the specific needs of consumers in each segment.
3. It is necessary to determine the specific characteristics of consumers.
4. The target segment of consumers must be large enough to cover the costs of producing the product to satisfy consumer demand.
5. The segment must be suitable for the company to sell the products it manufactures.

In our opinion, the main directions of the strategy for innovative development of the light industry market should be as follows:

1. Formation and development of light industrial engineering; re-equipment and modernization of existing enterprises; creation of new high-tech enterprises.
2. Formation of demand and supply and opportunities of the market of light industrial products, study of domestic and foreign market, formation of information and advertising system, economic assessment of export potential, forecasting of supply and demand for industry products.
3. Increase the processing of natural fibers, produce new types of fibers based on innovations, and develop new production technologies based on the adaptation of local raw materials.
4. Creating new jobs through the training of highly qualified personnel, continuous professional development and retraining, and expansion and restructuring of industry enterprises.

The importance of marketing research in organizing, managing, planning, and controlling overall marketing activities is one of the main features of modern marketing theory. In today's environment, when the consumer market is increasingly enriched with new goods and services, the importance of marketing research in identifying new opportunities and rationally using them is increasing day by day.

Consumers-buyers can purchase all types of goods and resources produced in the community. Therefore, the total volume of the social product, including the preparation of the means of production, is the main determining factor of marketing.

In the innovative development of the light industry of our republic, marketing research can be carried out in five major directions:

- firstly, by conducting advertising research, that is, to inspire buyers, advertising tests, types of advertising and their comparative effectiveness;

- secondly, through strategic planning and organizational policy, that is, making short and long-term forecasts, analyzing enterprise results and market opportunities, new diversification development opportunities, analyzing the operational overall and internal environment of the organization, as well as conducting export market monitoring;

- thirdly, by conducting research on corporate responsibility, that is, increasing the social responsibility of the organization in terms of shaping buyers and protecting the environment;

- fifth, by studying sales opportunities, conducting marketing research, that is, identifying potential or opportunity markets, analyzing market structure and changes in sales volume, conducting test marketing, and studying sales promotion procedures.

Of course, each organization, depending on its capabilities and established goals, conducts marketing research in one direction or another or in a specific industry. This takes into account the organization's strategy for a certain period of time and the required tactical actions. The goal of the enterprise is usually expressed in the form of financial indicators, and these indicators give an idea of what the enterprise intends to achieve over a certain period of time, for example, one year, two years, and five years.

Taking into account production capabilities, it is necessary to analyze the financial situation, the established policy towards employees, and the distribution channels of goods. When analyzing a separate sector, plans should be developed for each department, indicating the estimated values of income and expenses and aimed at specific goals, while the activities for the next year are clearly and concisely planned.

In marketing, the planning process requires, in addition to analyzing external factors, an internal analysis of the enterprise. By studying the enterprise, it is necessary to answer questions such as whether the level of training of sales managers meets the demand, what is the condition of the equipment, and whether the quality of our goods is satisfactory compared to that of our competitors.

The importance of a marketing program in the proper organization and implementation of marketing activities is immeasurable. This program consists of several sections, among which the "enterprise's market strategy" section identifies the main competitive advantages of the enterprise and assesses its opportunities for sales in the selected market. For this, the following specifications are defined:

- the expected profitability of the activity in the selected target market;
- the planned sales volume of the firm;
- dynamics of the firm's market share;
- demand dynamics and potential demand size.
- The company's competitive advantages can be described in terms of its products, price level, range of services, sales channel effectiveness, relevance of communication policy to current conditions, and brand popularity among potential customers. In this section of the program, it is also necessary to assess the company's activities in the selected market in terms of the provision of resources (financial, production, marketing, human). When developing a product policy, the following information is taken into account:

Figure 1.2. Scheme of marketing activities of textile enterprises.

- the degree of novelty of the product;
- the range of products being produced;
- the number of similar goods or substitute goods in this market segment;
- the degree to which it meets the needs of specific buyers in this market segment;
- quality of goods;
- technological complexity;
- the level of requirements for pre-sale and after-sale service;
- the feasibility of standardization or commodity flexibility;
- patent protection and patent purity for new products;

• compatibility of the existing organizational structure of the company with the new production;

- the amount of costs of creating a new product;
- Compulsory product certification in the target market;
- profitability of production and sale of new goods in the target market;
- investment payback period;
- the period of mastering the new assortment and its optimization;
- costs per product etc.

When developing a sales policy, the following are taken into account:

– application to the sales network for this market segment;
– the organizational structure of the company's sales and the number of qualified sales personnel;

- assessment of the company's experience in this market segment;
- assessment of the expediency of using the services of intermediaries;
- opportunities to increase the volume of sales with the help of intermediaries;
- the policy of intermediaries towards the firm;
- availability of financial resources to create a sales system;
- comparative assessment of profitability of personal selling system and alternative offers;
- supply of available goods to the market;
- number of potential customers;
- the nature of the distribution of the order;
- the habits and preferences of end consumers;
- the variability and instability of the product;
- coping efforts of the company's management;
- sales channel control, etc.

When developing a pricing policy, it is necessary to take into account the following:

- choosing a pricing method that meets the firm's capabilities and goals, taking into account competitors' practices;
- price level for one product;
- price dynamics corresponding to the stage of the product's life cycle;
- the price ratio in the assortment (nomenclature) according to the degree of novelty of the goods, differences in quality and technical level;
- price level relationship with competing similar goods in the target market;
- level of elasticity of demand;
- level of functional and pure competition;
- choosing a pricing strategy to launch a new product into the target market;
- service policy, brand popularity, length of sales channel and type of sales intermediaries, delivery conditions, discount system, etc.

3. The "Communication Policy" section recommends dividing the budget among the individual organizers of the product promotion policy and justifying their selection, as well as resolving issues related to communication tools.

When implementing a marketing program and determining a budget, it is important to consider the following:

- the total cost of implementing all marketing measures envisaged in this program;
- market research costs;
- costs of future market forecasting;
- costs of studying the firm's own production and sales capabilities;
- costs for creating a marketing program;
- expenses for salaries of employees of the company's marketing department;
- the costs of paying fees for the services of special marketing and advertising organizations;
- costs of paying fees for the services of commercial intermediaries;
- costs of evaluating the initial and final effectiveness of this marketing program;
- costs for implementing control and monitoring of the marketing program;
- costs for introducing current changes during the implementation of the marketing program, etc.

The marketing mix plays an important role in marketing policy. Today, John Baller has proposed a new, expanded marketing mix, which is called the corporate marketing mix. Model "10R" includes the following elements:

1. philosophy – organizational philosophy-idea;
2. personality – personnel who support the necessary corporate philosophy;
3. people – people;
4. products – goods;
5. prices – prices;
6. place – location;
7. promotion - move;
8. performance - evaluation and execution of enterprise activity;
9. perception – feeling;
10. positioning - positioning.

The marketing mix, in its most common form, includes 4 marketing submixes. These are: product mix, contract mix, communication mix, distribution mix. The product mix forms the product policy and includes measures related to the product. These measures include: design, its decoration, product quality, packaging, customer service, warranty policy, product diversification, assortment policy, etc.

The contract policy implements the agreement of the terms of the act of sale of goods and their formalization in the form of a contract. These measures include: price policy, markup and discount system, terms of goods delivery and payment, as well as credit policy.

The distribution policy implements the delivery of goods from the place of preparation to the recipient. This policy is the justification and analysis of the sales channel, marketing-logistics, sales policy, sales media policy, production force deployment policy. Includes customer and market location policies, delivery policies, finished goods warehousing policies, and more.

It should be noted that the Republic of Uzbekistan is constantly working to increase the export potential of our Republic by creating benefits for exporters of goods.

In the near future, an important factor for strengthening the export potential of our Republic is the strengthening of economic stimulation, export support by the state.

Conclusion. Today, a number of tax incentives aimed at state support of exporting enterprises are provided. A regressive scale of taxation has been introduced depending on the share of exports in relation to the volume of sales of goods.

The share of export in the total volume of product sales: if it is from 15% to 30%, the rate is 30%; Above 30%, the rate is halved.

Property tax for exporting enterprises is also carried out depending on the share of exports in the total volume of products: from 15% to 25% - the rate is reduced to 30%. From 25% to 50% - the rate is reduced by 50%; If it is more than 50% - property tax is not charged.

Value-added tax is levied at the lowest rate on exports. Value-added tax on material and technical resources required for the production of exported products can be paid in a 90-day interest-free deferral.

Implementation of credit financial support for national exporters is carried out in the following directions:

- creation of effective conditions of promotion of commercial banks financing export operations accepted in international practice;

- improvement of the existing mechanism of social protection of national exporters and commercial banks financing exports;

- providing investment insurance;

- One of the main obstacles to exporting products is that the products produced do not meet international requirements for certification and standardization.

The second of the conditions for the effectiveness of the national export policy is to fulfill the following conditions that allow to increase the export potential of our country:

- training and retraining of national personnel;

- development and implementation of optimal and effective conditions for marketing research that will allow identifying and developing new product markets;

- actively accelerate exports through the development of foreign trade infrastructure;

- introduction of advanced methods of export policy tactics and strategies of developed countries;

- development of a modeling system to determine the short-term and long-term perspectives of the state and dynamics of the parameters of the commodity markets in the main areas of the export activity of our republic;

- develop a strategy for developing new transport corridors in order to increase the efficiency of domestic transport infrastructure and diversify export and import cargo;

- reducing the cost of transporting export-import cargo through the development of infrastructure and the creation of a logistics system, as well as cargo processing on the territory of the republic and at major international seaports;

- Improving the development of the contractual and legal framework for cooperation with foreign countries in trade, investments, development of new transport corridors, and transit of goods;

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